

Marketing Mix Analysis of Somethinc Brand Skincare Manufacturer in East Jakarta

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ABSTRACT: The current expansion of the skincare product market has also led to the emergence of many local skincare brands in the cosmetics industry in Indonesia. Several brands compete by presenting quality products with international standards. So now competition for foreign and local skincare product businesses is becoming increasingly fierce. One of the skincare products that has been named the best-selling skincare brand in 2021 is the Somethinc brand, which is known to have only taken two years to achieve this crowning. This condition requires every company to have a marketing mix strategy that is designed in an integrated manner to produce the desired response in the target market.

The purpose of this research is to determine the 4P marketing mix strategy implemented by the Somethinc company and analyze the influence of the 4P marketing mix implemented by the Somethinc company on influencing consumers. The research method used is Mix Method, namely qualitative and quantitative methods. The qualitative method was carried out by conducting interviews with the Somethinc brand, while the quantitative method was carried out by distributing questionnaires to 100 respondents who were consumers of the Somethinc company.

The collected data is then used to create internal and external company analysis. Internal analysis was carried out using SWOT Analysis which was used to collect information about the condition of the Somethinc company, while external analysis was carried out using TOWS Analysis which was used to collect information regarding consumer responses to the Somethinc brand.

Based on this analysis, the researcher explains the 4P marketing mix strategy (Product, Price, Place and Promotion) that is implemented and presents the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats faced by the Somethinc company both internally and externally.

KEYWORDS: Marketing Mix 4P, Skincare.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rise of *skincare* cosmetic products in Indonesia is known to have experienced a very rapid development. The expansion of the skincare product market today has also led to the emergence of many local skincare brands in the cosmetic industry in Indonesia. Where, some of these brands compete by presenting quality products and international standards. So that now the business competition for foreign and local skincare products is getting tighter.

One of the skincare products that has been named the best-selling skincare brand from 2021-2024 is the Somethinc brand, which is known to have only taken two years to achieve this coronation. In addition, in 2022 it was reported that brand something also obtained the first position with a *market share of* 16.85% with total sales of 64,700 *serum* products (Sutiani, 2022). This condition is also a demand for somethinc companies to design various marketing strategies to achieve the desired market share and increase sales volume. Not only by offering unique and quality products, a targeted marketing strategy is also needed to increase competitiveness.

The study is intended to analyze the 4P marketing mix strategy (*price, product, place, promotion*) applied by the local cosmetic brand *Somethinc* in sales in order to compete with other brand competitors. These four aspects were chosen because they are the most influential and most relevant aspects to the object of research.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Previous research in this study was used by researchers as a reference or guideline in research. Previous research is research that has been conducted by previous researchers, which has a relationship or similarity with the research to be carried out. The previous studies used in this study are:

1. Research conducted by Herliyana, Muthia Harnida and Basuki (2020) with the title "The Effect of 4P Marketing Mix (Product, Price, Place, Promotion) on Purchasing Decisions on Wardah Cosmetic Products (Study on Wardah Product User Community in Banjarmasin)"
2. Research conducted by Rendy Harsono (2016) with the research title "The Impact of Marketing Mix (4PS) on Customer Loyalty Toward Toyota Avanza"
3. Research conducted by Semuel Batlajery and Marlyn E. Alfons (2021) with the title "Implementation of Product Model, Price, Place, Promotion in Improving Noken Sales (OAP)"

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a type of *mixed method* research. *mixed method* is a type of research using two methods simultaneously, namely quantitative and qualitative. Quantitative research is research that emphasizes its analysis on numerical data (numbers) processed by statistical methods, to obtain scientific information behind the numbers through questionnaires and surveys that given to Somethinc repetitive customers. Meanwhile, qualitative research is research whose data can be obtained through interviews with external and internal informants which are Somethinc customers and Somethinc Brand Marketing Staff.

4. ANALYSIS AND BUSINESS SOLUTION

The study aims to propose business strategy that considers internal and external analysis, and conduct marketing fit using a SWOT and TOWS analysis for future implementation.

Value Proposition

Internal Analysis

Based on SWOT analysis, the competitive advantage of Somethinc is on their all-round segment of products, affordable price for middle to upper class, well distributed among indonesia, strategic branch to easily reach customers, and repetitive promotion through online and offline platform. Based on qualitative data collection through interviews and quantitative through questionnaire, yet the brand has it's own weakness of non-reachable price for lower class, too many products. The brand has bigger opportunities to expand because the market is still vast both local and internationally. As long as Somethinc able to promote their products well on online and offline channels, the brand can sustain their businesses.

External Analysis

Considering the external factors such as Customers and Competitors (Customer analysis & Competitors analysis), Something has an opportunity to run the business in a conducive environment, since the rise of local skincare market starting on 2021, it's proven that Somethinc able to sustain their business until now 2024. These external analysis suggested Somethinc has the ability to innovate and adapt to the new dynamic environment, emphasizing values by utilizing marketing capabilities, increasing customer service excellence, and utilizing technology to expand their market.

SWOT-TOWS Analysis

The SWOT-TOWS analysis suggested actions for Somethinc, factoring the internal condition through strengths and weaknesses and the external environment that provides opportunities and threats.

Strength - Opportunities (SO)

- Maintain and preserve the quality of service, availability and completeness of products,
- Strengthen to continue to innovate to improve product advantages by maintaining attractive logos and packaging,
- Set the right price with the product content in order to compete with competitors who sell the same claim,
- Maintain good relationships by establishing good communication with consumers, suppliers, and resellers,
- Maintain the quality of production materials,
- Expanding the marketplace to all over Indonesia

Weakness - Opportunities (WO)

- Create new product innovations such as packaging,
- Add and strengthen cooperation with Brand Ambassadors,
- Improve the speed of service, especially the packaging and online delivery,

- Increase promotion to be better known by the public,
- Conduct an in-depth review of negative consumer reviews for evaluation

Strength - Threats (ST)

- Maintain product availability
- Routinely evaluate marketing activities
- Make competitor as motivation
- Provide Reward for loyal customers

Weakness - Threats (WT)

- Provide discount to customers
- Price adjustment
- Increase speed of service

Provide detailed information

- Provide bonus for internal and external

Proposed Business Strategy

- Product Strategy:** In offering its products, the Somethingnc brand prioritizes the quality of its products by using quality ingredients. Interview data findings reveal that every product owned by the Somethingnc brand is made through R&D, testing, certification, ingredients and the latest technology processes with very high standards. In addition, all Somethingnc brand products are known to be halal certified. Based on the results of 100 respondents' responses to the Somethingnc brand's product strategy, it is known that consumers think that the Somethingnc brand offers products that provide satisfactory results. Products owned by the Somethingnc brand meet health test standards.
- Price Strategy:** Data findings reveal that the pricing strategy implemented by the Somethingnc brand is to set prices that are appropriate to the target market. Apart from that, the prices offered by the Somethingnc brand adjust to the quality of the materials used and the products produced. The Somethingnc company is known to also offer several bundlings of Somethingnc products with other products in other product series such as the Somethingnc skincare series. This bundling price strategy is implemented to increase sales and profits. The bundling price offered to consumers who are interested in making a purchase and feel they save their budget compared to just purchasing one product. Based on the responses of 100 respondents who are consumers of the Somethingnc brand, it is known that the prices applied by the Somethingnc Brand are considered more competitive than other brands.
- Place Strategy:** A strategic, comfortable and easy to reach location will be a special attraction for Somethingnc brand customers. Choosing a location is the most expensive investment, because the location can be said to determine whether there will be many visitors or not. So the offline location chosen by the Somethingnc brand has a wide distribution, is easy to find and has a location in a busy place or lots of people passing by the sales place. Meanwhile, buying and selling transactions are also carried out online which is utilized by the Somethingnc brand on various e-commerce sites and the Somethingnc official website has expanded the distribution of its products available on various e-commerce platforms, through the Somethingnc official website & e-commerce. The use of Somethingnc's website and social media also helps consumers and potential consumers in providing information related to the products they need
- Promotion Strategy:** Somethingnc utilized TikTok in their digital marketing and started using TikTok media as a promotional medium by regularly uploading video content containing tutorials, tips & tricks, product reviews and information & promotions related to their products. Posting a product on social media will make the product more widely known and customers will also be interested in buying. Apart from that, in implementing its promotions, the Somethingnc brand also collaborates with various artists or public figures who are of interest to the public or uses campaign models originating from local (domestic) and other countries.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, the marketing mix consists of 4Ps, namely Place, Price, Price and Promotion. To increase sales volume, the 4P marketing mix is the most important element to drive consumer behavior in making purchases.

Brand Something in marketing its products is known to also apply the 4P marketing mix strategy. The influence given by the 4P marketing mix applied by Brand Something is obtained through based on the results of multiple regression analysis. It is known that the acquisition of the significance value (Sig.) in the regression test is $0.000 < 0.05$. This confirms that the hypothesis is accepted, which means that the 4P marketing mix (Product, Price, Place, Promotion) applied by the Something brand simultaneously or together has an effect on consumer behavior.

The amount of influence given by this 4P Marketing Mix on consumer behavior is known based on the acquisition of the value obtained by the R value² (R Square) of 0.682 (68.2%). This shows that the percentage of the influence of the marketing mix (product, price, location and promotion) on consumer buying interest is 68.2%, while the remaining 31.8% is explained or influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

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